

An Innovative Passive Islanding Detection Technique for Microgrid Environment Based on the ratio of DG side Positive Sequence Reactive Power and PCC-Voltage

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Abstract— As renewable energy adoption and distributed generation are growing, the reliable and steady operation of microgrids is essential. Detection of the Islanding state during microgrid operation is essential, as it often goes unnoticed and can interrupt distributed generators, threaten human lives, and degrade power quality. The article presents a passive islanding-detection method, which is centered on the observation of the ratio of DG-side positive sequence reactive power and positive sequence PCC-voltage. The technique is tested on a modified IEEE 13-bus system under various islanding and non-islanding conditions, focusing on fast detection time and reliable operation, using MATLAB/Simulink. The results are also validated in real time using the OPAL-RT platform and are found to be steady, accurate and satisfactory.

Keywords—Islanding detection method · Passive technique · Distributed generators · Circuit breaker · Utility grid

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand of electricity, environmental problems, and dependency on oil fuels have enhanced the inclusion of renewable and non-renewable distributed generation (DG) sources into the contemporary power systems to a greater use and satisfaction of the energy demand. The decentralization of the energy sources such as solar photovoltaic systems, wind turbines, diesel generators and energy storage has also been made central in providing the energy demand of the system. Islanding refers to the situation in which a microgrid or a section of the distribution network is fed by local DGs. Intentional islanding can be used to aid in planned outages (or emergencies), although unintentional islanding poses serious challenges to run of power systems. It can be potentially a safety hazard to utility workers, cause electrical equipment damage, instability of voltage and frequency, and poor power quality. In this way, the safe functioning of microgrids is a critical requirement that presupposes high-performing, and reliable islanding detection. The increasing use of renewable sources, such as solar and wind, contributes to an additional complication to islanding detection since these sources are intermittent, have low inertia and contain power electronic interfaces. Compared to non-renewable sources of power, renewable DGs constrain the natural frequency or voltage regulation attributes, and therefore, the system is more susceptible to disturbances. Moreover, modern distribution systems usually comprise nonlinear loads, capacitor switching, and faults, which may operate in the situation of islanding and result in inaccurate detection if not detected. To address these issues, several islanding detection techniques have been created and may be broadly divided into passive, active, hybrid, and communication-based.. The main advantages of passive techniques are their simplicity, low cost, and minimal effect on power quality, but they are associated with large non-detection zones in complex systems. Therefore, an effective passive islanding detection method that will distinguish well between islanding and non-islanding disturbances is a key research goal.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The rising worldwide energy demand has accelerated the shift toward non-conventional and renewable energy sources such as wind and solar power.[1]. These resources are eco-friendly, but since they are intermittent, they are not very dependable when used separately; therefore, they should be integrated into the mixture with traditional power generation systems [2]. Microgrids and distributed generation (DG) are also viable solutions in this case to improve the system's reliability and operational efficiency [3]. Nevertheless, the dynamic nature of renewable power sources makes the challenge of controlling the system, particularly regarding power quality and stability [4].

In this sort of hybrid power system, islanding is also a significant protection concern, in which a DG provides power to a section of the grid, even after that section has been taken out of the main utility [5]. Silent islanding may be fatal to the maintenance personnel and may damage equipment. To resolve such risks, such international standards as IEC 62116:2008 and IEEE 1547.1:2005 have established that islanding should be identified as soon

as possible within less than 2s, after which DG is to be de-energized [6]. Consequently, efficient development of the fast, reliable and low-cost techniques of islanding-detection is of the utmost priority to the field of ensuring safe and stable operation of power with a high concentration of renewable operation [7].

Passive islanding detection techniques that identify the occurrence of islanding by observing the variation in the electrical parameters at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC), such as voltage, frequency, current, phase angle, harmonic content and power. Passive methods do not add any disturbances to the system as compared to active methods, which are desirable as they are simple techniques, low-cost, and do not affect the quality of power significantly. Nonetheless, conventional threshold-based passive methods, including over-/under-voltage and over-/under-frequency relay, typically possess large non-detection zones (NDZs), which undermine performance [7]. More advanced signs have been proposed to increase the accuracy of detection including voltage imbalance, total harmonic distortion (THD), jump in voltage phase-angle, and the power change with frequency rate. The parameters make it more sensitive to islanding and curb NDZ [8]. Even passive-based approaches have been made to be better, yet even passive approaches may cause false-detection during non-islanding disturbances, including faults, load switching, or voltage sags, which highlight the importance of more robust detection approaches [9].

Fig.1 Types of islanding method

Active islanding detection techniques are based on the principle of injecting small perturbations in the distributed generation (DG) system. Although these methods are quite efficient in decreasing the non-detection zone (NDZ), they can have a negative impact on the power quality. The Slip Mode Frequency Shift (SMFS) based technique is one of the active techniques those are widely used and may change the inverter operating frequency which depend on the load conditions that are connected to find islanding [7].

In order to deal with the drawbacks of the isolated use of active and passive methods, hybrid islanding detection methods are created to enhance the overall reliability [8]. These techniques are usually based on a steady tracking of electrical values including the voltage, frequency, and phase angle and alarm alert in case of an unusual operating condition [9]. Recent developments in hybrid methods cover applying the units of phasor measurement (PMUs) that give synchronized measurements and increase the precision of islanding detection [10]. Also, machine learning-based methods including artificial neural networks (ANNs) have been introduced with an aim of enhancing speed of detection [11]. Islanding detection schemes based on communication include schemes like transfer trip, SCADA-based signaling and PMU-enabled synchronization, which allow information flow between DG units and

the utility grid. These approaches, however, have high infrastructure requirements, complex coordination and are expensive to operate, which restricts their use in large-scale distribution networks.

Given these difficulties, there is a definite necessity of islanding detection method that is quick, precise, computationally effective and does not affect the quality of power. The present paper would suggest a superior object of passive grid-attached photovoltaic (PV) system islanding detection strategy based on observing voltage and current values at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) and the distributed generator (DG). The technique utilizes the relative value of DG side positive sequence reactive power and PCC-voltage as a major variable that identifies the occurrence of islanding. The results of simulations prove that the developed method is the cost-effective, efficient, and stable solution to the issue of islanding detection in the current PV-based distributed generation units.

The specified technique is confirmed with the help of a modified IEEE 13-bus test system, with the addition of two inverter-based PV distributed generators (DG1 and DG2), each with a power of 2 MW. DG units are interconnected with the utility grid at the normal test conditions and the irradiance of the sun is fixed to 1000 W/m² and temperature is maintained to 25 °C. The voltage and current waves in the PCC are sampled at a frequency of 10 kHz in order to record the transient behavior and decompose them into their sequence components. The ratio of positive sequence reactive power to voltage is calculated and serves as the primary indicator for islanding detection. To eliminate higher-order harmonics and inverter switching noise, the measured signals are processed with a low-pass digital filter, retaining only the fundamental and relevant transient components for analysis.

Table 1: Specification of Test System Parameters

Parameters	Values
Rated voltage at PCC	4160 V
System Frequency	50 Hz
Power Factor	0.9
Filter series inductance	0.009 H
Filter series resistance	0.9195
Filter shunt capacitance	5.53 e ⁻⁶ F
Filter shunt resistance	1e ⁻⁶ Ω
Switching Frequency	10 kHz
Transformer Rating	480/4160

III. PROPOSED ISLANDING DETECTION METHODS

A modified IEEE 13-bus test system, as shown in Fig. 2, is modelled in MATLAB/Simulink to test the proposed islanding detection technique (IDT). The conditions of opening circuit breaker CB1 at 0.7 s under various operating conditions are generated by islanding conditions. At DG1 and Point of Common Coupling (PCC), three-phase voltage and current signals are measured. The result of these measurements is used to calculate a detection index, which is then compared with a set threshold. An index below the threshold is defined as a non-islanding condition, and an index above the threshold will be defined as an islanding event. To test the accuracy and strength of the method, a number of islanding and non-islanding cases are analyzed. Additionally, the voltage and current phasors are measured and converted to positive-sequence components for detailed analysis.

Fig. 2. Modified IEEE 13 bus system

The positive sequence component is part of the symmetrical components method used in power system analysis to simplify the analysis of unbalanced three-phase systems. From a common three-phase voltage matrix V_{abc} . The symmetric components can be derived from three-phase voltages as positive sequence (V_{a1}), negative sequence (V_{a2}), and zero sequence (V_{a0}). The formula for calculating the sequence voltages is presented as

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{a0} \\ V_{a1} \\ V_{a2} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & a & a^2 \\ 1 & a^2 & a \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_b \\ V_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The value of a (complex operator) is $e^{j2\pi/3}$.

Here, V_a , V_b , and V_c are the phase voltages of PCC.

Now, from equation 1, the positive sequence voltage of PCC can be identified as

$$V_{pcc} = \frac{1}{3}(V_a + a^2V_b + aV_c) \quad (2)$$

Similarly, for the current matrix I_{abc} . The symmetric components can be derived as I_{a1} , I_{a2} , I_{a0} .

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_{a0} \\ I_{a1} \\ I_{a2} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & a & a^2 \\ 1 & a^2 & a \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_a \\ I_b \\ I_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Here, I_a , I_b , I_c are phase currents of PCC.

From equation 3, the positive sequence current obtained from PCC can be written as

$$I_{pcc} = \frac{1}{3}(I_a + a^2I_b + aI_c) \quad (4)$$

Similarly, for DG-side, the positive sequence components of voltage and current can be obtained as

$$V_{dg} = \frac{1}{3}(V_a + a^2V_b + aV_c) \quad (5)$$

$$I_{dg} = \frac{1}{3}(I_a + a^2I_b + aI_c) \quad (6)$$

From equations (5) and (6), the DG-side positive sequence apparent power vector per phase is expressed as

$$S_{dg} = (V_{dg} * I_{dg}^*)/3 = P_{dg} + jQ_{dg} \quad (7)$$

And from equations (5) and (7), the index can also be identified as

$$Q_{index} = \left| \frac{Q_{dg}}{V_{pcc}} \right| \quad (8)$$

In the case of maximum active power flow by the DG, the reactive power per phase is very low during normal conditions and has a significant impact during islanding, as shown in Fig. 3. Here, the value of DG-current is reasonable in normal conditions but has a very small impact during islanding mode. The positive-sequence PCC voltage drops rapidly after islanding, as shown in Fig. 3. Therefore, the index, which is the ratio of positive-sequence DG reactive power to positive-sequence PCC voltage, increases during islanding and can differentiate islanding and non-islanding conditions.

Fig.3 Magnitudes of (a) DG-current (b) PCC-voltage (c) DG-reactive power

During normal grid-connected operation, the combined Q_{index} stays nearly constant because the PCC-voltage and DG side reactive power relationship. When islanding occurs, the loss of the main grid results in clear changes in Q_{index} , which can exceed the preset threshold and provide an alert signal for an islanding condition.

IV.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The UL1741 standard is used to test the behavior of distributed generation (DG) systems when the conditions of zero power mismatch (ZPM) are met, and the active (ΔP) and reactive (ΔQ) power variations are nearly equal to zero. In this proposed modeled network, the DG provides 4 MW of active power as per the load demand and 0.2905 Mvar of reactive power. At $t = 0.7s$, circuit breaker CB1 opens its contact, causing islanding by disconnecting the DG from the utility grid. After this instant, the DG operates in an islanded mode, independently supplying to the local load. During this condition, the ratio of positive-sequence DG-side reactive power to positive-sequence PCC voltage is monitored, and the corresponding RORPPSV-based islanding detection index is calculated. Since the main grid is completely disconnected after CB1 operation, a clear change in the index is observed, confirming the occurrence of islanding. This test is also conducted under grid-connected and fault conditions to establish the threshold of the RORPPSV index-based technique, which provides a clear differentiation between non-islanding and islanding situations.

Fig. 4a shows that the index exceeds the threshold, indicating an islanding event, whereas Fig. 4b shows the alarm being activated under ZPM conditions. The proposed IDT detects islanding within 19 ms, demonstrating its ability to quickly identify it.

Fig.4. Index and AS for ZPM condition

The suggested approach was tested on the different conditions of active power mismatch (APM) by changing the RLC load in order to create positive and negative mismatches, i.e., +10,+25, +50, -10, -25 and -50, as compared to

the mismatch-free case. The islanding event occurred at 0.7 s when opening the circuit breaker CB1. Fig. 5 indicates that the detection indices exceeded the threshold in all positive APM scenarios (+10, +25, +50).

A negative APM was also tested by changing the RLC load and it is shown that the detection indices and alarm values were able to recognize islanding within 30 ms of the opening of CB1 which is exhibited in Fig. 6. Comprehensively, the IDT is both consistent and sensitive to detect islanding in both positive and negative APM conditions with the usual limit of 30ms of the maximum detection time.

Fig.5. Indices for 10%,25%,50%, APM conditions

Fig.6. Indices for -10 %, -25%-50%, APM condition

A. ISLANDING AT DIFFERENT RPM CONDITIONS

The IDT suggested was also experimented under other reactive power mismatch (RPM) conditions. In the case of negative RPM values of -10, -20 and -50, the load was modified correspondingly and Fig. 7 indicates that the calculated indices and the alarm indicators were higher than the threshold during islanding cases of negative RPMs.

The load was also changed under positive RPM conditions of +10, +20 and +50. The indices as indicated in Fig. 8 were below the threshold during normal operation and above 19 ms after occurring the islanding event as indicated in Fig. 7d. In all cases of RPM, the highest detection time of 19 ms in case of mismatch of 50%.

Fig.7. Indices for +10 %, +20%, +50%, RPM conditions

Fig.8. Indices for -10%,-20%,-50%, RPM conditions

B. DISCONNECTION OF DG2 FROM THE SYSTEM

The modified IEEE-13 bus system is equipped with two distributed generators (DGs) operating within the network. At 0.7s, circuit breaker CB3 opens and DG2 is disconnected from the system intentionally. Such disconnection leads to the observable change in index utilized by the proposed IDT. When the index increases and passes its predetermined criterion, a warning signal is activated and this signals indicates the occurrence of an islanding condition. Fig. 9 shows the exact time, when the index reaches to the threshold, which indicates the ability of fast islanding detection in case of the occurrence of the DG separation. Overall, the alignment of the warning signal with the threshold crossing confirms the reliability and robustness of the proposed method. This successful detection highlights its practical applicability for real distribution network conditions.

Fig.9. Index for DG disconnection

C. UNBALANCED LOADING

The investigated IDT has already proven that it can be used reliably in earlier cases and will be validated for in case of unbalanced loading conditions. In order to comprehensively test the effectiveness of the developed IDT in such a realistic situation, an additional unbalance inductive load which is equal to 2 percent of the overall rating of the system, such as 80 kW, was connected at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC). This intentional imbalance put some slight imbalance in the system, and it gives a chance to evaluate whether the IDT is capable of detecting the islanding events with some imprecision in case the load conditions are not ideal. CB1 circuit breaker was opened at 0.7s to simulate an islanding event, which isolates the distributed generation (DG) of the main utility grid. With this disconnection, the index of islanding detection of the system became extremely high beyond the predetermined threshold, which is a clear indication of the occurrence of an islanding condition as shown in Fig. 10. The reaction of the proposed IDT was extremely quick as the detection time of the device was only 28 ms even in the condition of unbalanced loading. This very short response time demonstrates that the technique is sensitive and reliable, and thus that the technique is able to detect islanding events in non-ideal situations those are more realistic and prone to problematic system unbalance and demonstrated the concept of the technique as effective in detecting islanding events. In general, the findings indicate that the suggested method is not only able to provide quick and precise detection, but is also resilient and can be used under diverse and realistic loading scenarios.

Fig.10. Index and AS for unbalanced loading

D. CAPACITIVE AND INDUCTIVE SWITCHING

Capacitive and inductive load-switching tests were conducted under non-islanding conditions to assess the reliability of the proposed detection method. In scenario one, a 15 kVAR capacitive load was suddenly connected at PCC-632; in the second scenario, a 15 kVAR inductive load was connected at the same point. According to Fig. 11(a) and Fig. 11(b), the method did not issue any false alarms during either switching event. These findings show that the proposed method remains consistent with reactive power variations and is not affected by disturbances caused by normal load switching, demonstrating its accuracy and reliability under real operating conditions.

Fig.11. Indices for capacitive and inductive load switching

5. Non-Islanding Test Cases

E. DIFFERENT FAULT VERIFICATION

In fault conditions, the currents and voltages at fault points are high. In order to examine the strength of the suggested islanding detection technique, various fault cases, including line-to-ground (LG) and three-phase-to-ground (LLLG) faults were validated. The results show the existence of the fault conditions, however, there was no activation of the false alarm with islanding at 0.7s because of selection of appropriate threshold. This demonstrates that the given approach can be used with a high degree of reliability to distinguish between islanding and faults which proves the proposed methodology demonstrates effective performance and yields satisfactory results

F. LG FAULT WITH DIFFERENT FAULT RESISTANCES

The faults applied at the DG-location of the distribution system were single-line-to-ground (SLG) to evaluate the resilience of the proposed islanding-detection method. Islanding was initiated at 0.7 s, and the system's response was tested at fault resistances of 1, 5, and 10. The detection index produced no false alarms at the various testable resistances, as shown in Fig. 12. This consistency confirms that the proposed approach is both predictable and precise, successfully differentiating actual islanding events from microgrid disruptions caused by faults.

Fig.12. Index for LG fault

G. LLG FAULT WITH DIFFERENT FAULT RESISTANCES

A double the line-to-ground fault is added to the DG location, with fault resistances of 1 Ω, 5 Ω and 10 Ω to determine the performance of the method. As shown in Fig. 13, the proposed technique does not produce any false alarms at any fault resistance, demonstrating its reliability and accuracy to fault-related disturbances in the microgrid.

Fig.13. Index for LLLG fault

H. LLLG FAULT WITH DIFFERENT FAULT RESISTANCE

LLLG fault of variable fault resistance is incepted at the DG location and islanding is initiated at 0.7 s. Fig. 14 shows that all the false alarms are absent, thus proving that the suggested IDT is a reliable tool to detect islanding and work correctly and efficiently in harsh fault conditions

Fig.14. Index for LLLG fault

I. LOAD SWITCHING

At 0.7 s, 35% of the rated load is switched at the PCC to test the system’s response. This change did not significantly affect the detection index, and no alert signal was triggered, as shown in Fig. 15. These results confirm that the proposed method performs reliably even under substantial load variations.

Fig.15. (a) Load switching index, (b) Alert signal

J. VERIFICATION OF NONLINEAR LOAD SWITCHING

Harmonics can be caused by non-linear loads like charging transformers or UPS systems which can introduce harmonics that influence the quality of power and stability of voltages. In order to evaluate the proposed IDT in such conditions a 4.5 kW nonlinear load was attached at PCC, and removed at 0.7 s. There were no false alarms activated as indicated in Fig.16 because the detection index was less than the threshold indicating that the IDT is effective in managing nonlinear load switching.

Fig.16. Non Linear Load switching index

V. HARDWARE VALIDATION USING OPAL-RT REAL-TIME SIMULATOR

The proposed IDT was experimentally tested on an OPAL-RT real-time simulator (OP4517). The MATLAB/Simulink model was simulated on a desktop machine (Intel Core i7-8700, 12 GB RAM, 64-bit operating system) and divided into subsystems SM Master, SS Slave, and SC Console, each running on a separate simulator core with a fixed-step solver. The real-time signals were observed using an analogue output card, which had 16 channels, and recorded through an InfiniVision DSOX3034T MDO3014 oscilloscope. Islanding was also tested under zero power mismatch, and at 0.7 s, distinct voltage changes were observed (Fig. 17). The real-time detection index and the alert signal confirmed the correctness and consistency of the proposed IDT in a real-time environment.

Fig.17.OPAL-RT Simulator

Fig.18. OPAL-RT Test Result

VI. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

The suggested islanding detection strategy is compared to the existing passive IDT presented in [17]. Though the approach presented in [17], which is based on the content of the voltage ripple, is effective for the system model presented in [17]. However, its validation is required for the system model of the modified IEEE-13 bus system presented in this paper. Its index of detection, as shown in Fig. 19(a), does not reliably detect islanding and is unable to clearly distinguish between islanding and fault conditions at 10 Ω fault resistance (Fig. 19(b)). It also leads to possible misdetections and is less reliable when used in real-life distribution networks.

Fig.19a DRCV index presented in [17] (a) islanding condition, (b) fault condition

The major impact of the article is as follows:

- ❖ The suggested IDT makes use of positive-sequence voltage and current signals of both the utility grid and DGs in order to realize rapid islanding identification.
- ❖ The proposed approach has the advantage of being effective in the presence of DG disconnection as well as events when capacitors are switched.
- ❖ The technique has been shown to be sensitive and correct to operate in non-islanding conditions, such as faults of different resistances and locations, load, capacitor and nonlinear load switching.
- ❖ It was further tested in an experimental manner on an OPAL-RT real-time platform and its effectiveness was found to be satisfactory.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a new passive islanding detection method that is effective in distinguishing between an islanding and non-islanding situation using ratio positive sequence PCC voltage and DG side reactive power measurements. The approach is verified in a wide range of conditions such as zero, half power mismatch, disconnection of the DG, and the normal operation and demonstrates a fast and steady detection time of around 19 ms, which is better than the current passive IDTs [24]-[26]. The conventional DRCV-based strategies exhibit poor performance in complex networks like the modified IEEE-13 bus system and cannot distinguish between islanding and fault events with different fault impedances. However, the developed IDT presents an excellent and robust, accurate, and stable behavior across all the experimental experiences. The practical feasibility and reliability of OPAL-RT is further confirmed by the fact that it has been implemented in real-time on an OPAL-RT platform. Besides, the suggested method has sensitivity and accuracy to fault-related disturbances, load fluctuations, and nonlinear load switching. It's almost zero non-detection region boosts the reliability of protection in realistic networks of distribution. The approach in general provides a scalable and promising solution to real-life applications of microgrids and distributed generation.

VIII. REFERENCES

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